

TOWARDS OPEN ACCESS: BUMPY BUT GETTING SMOOTHER!

Journal flipping – from subscription to open access

OPEN MEDICINE & OPEN MATHEMATICS

(previously: Central European Journal of Medicine, and Central European Journal of Mathematics)

OPEN MATHEMATICS – POST OA

- ▶ A slight drop in submissions after introducing APCs, but submissions and articles published increasing
- ▶ Rejection Rate slightly down, but Impact Factor increasing (RR from 79% to 65%; IF from 0.405 to 0.682 during 2013–2016)
- ▶ Strong backlash against OA from original Editors and Editorial Advisory Board
- ▶ A significant increase in number of articles from China and Turkey

Number of articles:

OPEN MEDICINE – POST OA

- ▶ A significant drop in submissions after introducing APCs
- ▶ Number of published articles inching up
- ▶ Rejection Rate falling (from 84% to 40% from 2013–2016)
- ▶ Impact Factor increasing (from 0.262 to 0.294)

Revenue: drop in the first year immediately after introducing APCs (2015), revenue increase in the second year (2016) and steady increase since – Q1 and H1 2017 vs. Q1 and H1 2016

Number of articles:

DE GRUYTER'S SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS

Problem A: strong resistance to OA gold model
Solution: appoint new editors supportive of OA, widen author base internationally, develop previously “neglected” subject areas

Problem B: authors unable to cover APCs
Solution: introduce waiver & discount policies and institutional membership scheme, assist with funding acquisition

Problem C: Impact Factor Suspension (Open Mathematics)
Solution: Patience and increasing content quality. We believed that given the increased citations potential pertinent to OA model, IF would rebound after one year. The journal reclaimed the IF, with the side effect of increased visibility, expanded authors base and become an invaluable source of content in areas previously unpublished.